

Towards a Microhistoriography of Bengali People: Excavating the Ruins of Remembrance and Forgetting

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If the task of the revolutionary historiographer is a pressing one, it is because the history that he or she seeks to redeem is in constant danger of perishing. It is the fate of the dispossessed to disappear. They are men and women who lack a lineage or succession, infertile creatures who thus require a different kind of memorial. They represent what Antoine Compagnon has called 'the history of that which has no descendants ... the history of the failures in history' – of those obscure strivings for justice which have melted and left no trace behind them in the annals of official history ...

Terry Eagleton, *Hope Without Optimism* (29)

What happened to Bengal's history? That is perhaps a rhetorical question that one may not strictly need to answer, because the answer is obvious. So many years have lapsed since Bankim's well known lament that Bengalis need history or else they will not be human enough. But history of Bengal still stands in disarray. When we realise that Bengalis are yet to develop a coherent historiography which will tell them of their past glory and defeats, of their land, people, culture and journey, we understand that something is rotten in the state of Bishshomanobic Bengalis. Indeed, Ognijug is a case in point. Such is the problematic of the history of Ognijug, that the official school textbooks of Bengal described our revolutionary nationalists as terrorists a few years ago.

History of Bengal remains disorganized and fragmented. There are still no comprehensive, authoritative accounts of our medieval and modern periods, which have not yet witnessed a work like Niharranjan Ray's *Bangalir Itihash (Adiporbo)* that catered to the ancient period.. None whatsoever undertaken at the level of government sponsored projects. But interestingly, scholars passionate about Bengal's history have painstakingly worked on the history of various periods and places since the Bengali revival of nineteenth century. They now constitute an obscure gamut of out-of-print works.

Most of them are not yet digitized and rarely reprinted. It is perhaps pertinent now to construct a microhistoriography of the Bengali people in the light of these forgotten projects. Because we have our history all scattered, it is only a revolutionary microhistoriography that can convert this crisis into a critical opportunity, and can somewhat amusingly transform a compulsion into a commitment. Those who only have a fragmented history, whose mainstream history is under occupation from alien forces who like to tell us that the martyrs of Ognijug were terrorists, must learn to do with fragments and miniscule histories themselves.

Let us remember these forgotten fragments. Each of these fragments has the potential to turn into a site of pilgrimage, a destination for explorers, a site of Shakti, much in the vein of the pieces from the mutilated body of Sati that gave birth to the rise of *Shaktipīthas*.

Our ancient history was brutally mutilated and largely obliterated by invaders like Bakhtiyar Khilji, the destroyer of ancient universities like Nalanda. Bengal's modern history, particularly the history of Ognijug is likewise being mutilated by another bunch of invaders. The contribution of Bengal to India's freedom struggle is not just downplayed but a Bengal-less history of struggle of independence has become a possibility, as part of an official truth in a tripartite arrangement operating within our left-Nehruvian-Sangh dominated academia. The impossible is achieved in this intellectual jugglery when the people, the ideas, the struggle and the sacrifice of Bengal are completely obliterated in a version of

history which claims that the idea of India emerged during 1930s (which is, effectively after Bengal was cut down to size in terms of importance and influence in all India politics). We shall come to that presently. But first of all, we must note that 1930s are a watershed, as this decade was witnessing the final eclipse of Bengal after a concerted effort of British which started during the last years of nineteenth century, as Bengal became too big a threat, intellectually, culturally, politically and philosophically. General Secretary of CPI(M), Sitaram Yechury in an article in the periodical *Frontline* says, “The emergence of the conception of the idea of India arose from a continuous battle between three visions that emerged during the 1920s on the conception of the character of independent India.”¹

Yechury then goes on to describe these three visions as those of (Gandhi) Congress, Left, and RSS. They share some curious commonalities. Congress finally became Gandhi's fiefdom after the expulsion of Subhash, which happened during this period. And Gandhi was instrumental in marginalizing Bengal in all India politics. Congress under Lal Bal Pal was fighting for total independence, but under Gandhi it ensured the convenience of the Raj by demanding dominion status. After C R Das's sad and untimely demise in 1925, Gandhi became practically the unchallenged ruler of Congress till Subhash's rebellion. Left (actually, the Communist Party) entered India with some active British patronage as my article in the Ognijug issue of JBS demonstrated. And RSS never fought in the freedom struggle and was subservient to the empire. The revolutionary nationalist movement which was launched in Bengal was dead, and these three vultures made a feast over its dead body, as they came to divide the pie of India's official history among them. So we shall forget that the idea of India was there in the reform movements which constituted the signature contribution of Bengal in the nineteenth century, the idea of India in the Bengal Renaissance must likewise be forgotten, we shall forget the contribution of Vande Mataram in India's freedom struggle (albeit that was a song written specifically for Bengal, but it was appropriated all over India and no honest history of the struggle of independence can be conceived without it), we shall forget the history of boycott movement, we shall forget that in India the “father of the nation” was a title that was originally conferred on Surendranath Banerjee, much before the name M K Gandhi even was remotely heard in India. We shall forget Bankim, Vivekananda, Aurobindo, because they are now without any powerful legacy-bearers who can restore history to its truth, and reclaim the place of pride that Bengalis deserves in history writing. It is now high time for us to turn to microhistory, to salvage whatever we can, from our past.

But what do we understand by the term microhistory? As we define this interdisciplinary field, in the very beginning we need to be adequately resistant against any blind import of a western template. While we must study the origin and development of the concept of microhistory in the west, we also must adapt it for our own situation so that it benefits our own investigations. We should be driven by an urge not to imitate, but to improvise and assimilate this western theory of microhistory.

In his insightful article titled “Four Arguments for Microhistory” published in the journal *Rethinking History*, it has been observed by István Szijártó that microhistory has four defining characteristics.

The first trait is that microhistory is more attuned to the “little facts” of history. Secondly, it is enjoyably presented, and thus is more popular and can aspire to reach out to the the reading public outside the circle of professional historians. “The specificity of history when compared to the other 'verbal fictions' is that it must be based on the 'little facts.' Microhistory is necessarily built more directly on the 'little facts' of the sources than traditional social history and it is more concrete” (210). Moreover, it is pointed out: “In microhistory the reader feels that he is coming directly to the people of the past, closer than it is otherwise possible in historical studies” (210).

Further, it is observed: “Modern social history has placed the experience (expérience, gelebtes Leben) of real human beings to the centre of its attention. The third advantage of microhistory is that it can convey the lived experience to readers” (210).

Lastly, microhistory connects the individual, the specific with the general. A small event is likewise engaged contextually to the longue durée that it might challenge and deconstruct as well. What we observe here is that a microhistorical study applies a method that does not treat its subject matter in an isolated manner but puts it within a perspective, investigating the larger framework.

Georg G Iggers considers that microhistory has sprung to life because of “generalizations that do not hold up when tested against the concrete reality of the small-scale life they claim to explain”.² Microhistory has thus rebelled against universalism, and has been more interested in the exceptions than in the generalized hegemony. It was with such an imperative, Carlo Ginzberg suggests, that the term microhistory was coined by George R Stewart in 1959, and later it was first methodically applied

look back, we see that all of our past issues were dealing with the specific, had a localized focus, and had microhistorical aims chalked out in their call for papers, without deliberately intending to do so. Our issues on Ognijug, Bengali Cinema, Bengali theatre, Science and Technology: Modern Bengali Perspectives, Literature and Movements: Bengali Crossroads, Kolkata, Bengali Music – these themes were fertile grounds for microhistorical enquiry.

An article meant for a journal like JBS (that focuses on Bengali cultural history) can very often be oriented microhistorically by the very physicality of the medium, as the piece will be compelled to choose a smaller unit of research, a compulsion that does not generally visit upon a voluminous book length study.

At the same time, shape and size cannot always be dependable as criteria for determining a certain work's status as microhistorical. A very small article on Bengal's history by Bankim Chandra can be read as very much macro-historical compared to a large treatise on the history of Nadia. The focus, the emphasis, the method, the design and the content are important factors when we decide on a work qualifying as microhistory.

Microhistory is a relatively smaller project, and can survive independently without institutional patronage, and can serve significantly to the cause of nationalist revival in any culture. One specific example of that would be this very journal. We have survived on our own for last four years. Because its primary aim is to challenge the master narratives, and at present the master narratives belong to liberal hegemony which denounces nationalist history to the margins, it can be an instrument of resistance.

Let us work towards a microhistoriography of the Bengali people.

Notes

1. <<http://www.frontline.in/the-nation/the-need-for-a-new-agenda/article7447315.ece>>. Accessed on 17 November 2015.
2. <<http://historynewsnetwork.org/article/23720>> Accessed on 17 September 2015.
3. Ginzberg, Carlo. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1343946?seq=1#page_scan_tab_contents>. Accessed on 17 September 2015.
4. Mari, Francesca. "The Microhistorian". <<https://www.dissentmagazine.org/article/the-microhistorian-2>>. Accessed on 17 September 2015.
5. Shoptodina 1: 5 (2015). <www.shoptodina.com>. Accessed on 17 November 2015.

Bibliography

Szijártó, István. “Four Arguments for Microhistory”. *Rethinking History* 6:2 (2002), pp. 209–215.

Eagleton , Terry. *Hope Without Optimism*. London: Yale University Press, 2015.

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